

Building Preservation Case Study of Pancasila Building in Pasuruan City

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ABSTRACT: Some cities in Indonesia have a long history of city development, in East Java, for example the cities of Surabaya, Malang, Blitar, Kediri and Pasuruan are cities that have a history of urban development that still maintains the identity of the city. old buildings or colonial buildings, these buildings can still be suspected through the characteristics of building shapes and the use of ornaments that are characterized by European buildings. For this European building to be preserved, it is necessary to conduct a feasibility study of the aesthetic value contained in the building. The case study taken in writing this article is the Pancasila Building in the city of Pasuruan. The method used is descriptive analysis topically. To support the discussion in this article, field observations and literature studies were conducted. The findings in this study were to determine the physical identity of the building and the meaning of building ornaments.

KEYWORDS: City Identity, Pancasila Building, Preservation Building Ornaments, Pasuruan City.

I. INTRODUCTION

Preservation is an effort that can revive old vitality that has faded. Including efforts to preserve historic buildings. Increasing the aesthetic and historical values of a historic building is very important to pull back the interest of the community to visit the area or building as evidence of history and civilization from time to time. Preservation of historic buildings is said to be very important. In addition to maintaining the historical value of the building, it can also maintain the building to be offered to future generations.

The Indonesian nation is a nation that is rich in history and culture. Certainly not a few historical buildings that hold important stories and spread throughout Indonesia. In fact, almost every city has historic buildings that serve as the identity of the city.

Contrary to what Indonesia knows that is rich in history and culture, there are still many Indonesians who are not aware of it. There are so many phenomena that occur and raise concerns, especially in the field of building architecture in Indonesia. As stated by [2][3][4], that architecture and cities in Indonesia today suffer from shortness of breath. Ancient buildings are historically destroyed and open spaces transformed into buildings. even though destroying ancient buildings is the same as removing one mirror to recognize history and traditions of the past. With the loss of historical buildings, the history of a place that has actually created an identity has disappeared, which has led to the erosion of cultural identity [1]. Therefore, preservation of historic buildings is needed so that they can still maintain the cultural heritage that has been inherited by our predecessors.

The city of Pasuruan was chosen as the location of the case study because the city of Pasuruan has a lot to save the city's heritage, namely colonial building. At present the city of Pasuruan is experiencing many changes in its architectural form, especially buildings of historical value are destroyed, if this is allowed then it will have an impact on the loss of the values of urban space that is not in accordance with the original concept. Therefore this research is very necessary so that the city of Pasuruan remains a city that maintains historical buildings so that its residents feel comfortable, safe, and beautiful.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The preservation approach in this article begins with an understanding of conservation from various sources, followed by conservation ethics and conservation value approaches and summarized in the framework of the conservation approach.

A. *Understanding of Preservation*

Preservation is the process of having the integrity of an object that is still returning there [7], or the whole process of understanding and maintaining a place to maintain its cultural meaning [5][11]. The process includes maintenance and preservation actions, based on the state of the object when preserved. Conservation measures can be of one type or several types at a time. The definition of preservation used in this article is the process of understanding, protecting, caring for and carrying out conservation actions in a historical building that still exists, so that its cultural meaning survives.

Benefits obtained from the preservation of historic buildings include [6][9][11] that historical building show identity, ethnicity, or social groups and provide scientific evidence of the past, and can be a part of the emotional connection that provides space and place experiences as they did in the past. The beauty and building techniques are admired, while cities characterized by historic buildings bring to the atmosphere of past life and can provide a feeling of retreat in time.

B. Conservation Value Approach

Value approach is an approach that reveals values that explain the cultural meaning of a historic building. Cultural meanings are composed and supported by a set of values, and those often associated with cultural heritage are historical, architectural, aesthetic, scarcity, locality, social values [11].

The role of conservation is to maintain these values, or even improve them [6][8][11]. These values help set priorities in conservation actions, and determine the level and nature of each action [6]. Conservation measures are chosen according to the physical conditions of the building and current conditions. The values used for the preservation study of Dutch colonial heritage buildings, which represent the past and present, are as follows: (1) Historical Value: as physical evidence of past life; (2) Value of Use: related to building benefits (functional, social, economic, educational aspects) for present-day activities; (3) Architectural Value: related to design quality, aesthetics, and contributions (architectural style, the work of famous architects, pioneering building techniques); (4) Vocational Value: related to the uniqueness of a building that is different from other places, namely the uniqueness of the design, architectural forms, construction techniques, and materials; (6) Values of Strength: related to the maturity of artwork on decorative elements and ornaments.

C. Preservation Ethics

The ethics of preservation are based on the integrity and authenticity of various aspects, the description and relevance of other aspects are as follows [5][6][8][11].

The integrity of the historic building, as a relic of the past that contains details that can be informed about the past, includes: physical integrity, design, structural, building relationships-environment and context. If you have to replace the material, the new material must match the architectural style.

The authenticity of historic buildings related to various aspects, from maintaining the original design to the original material. Authenticity does not mean returning the building to its original condition, but an appropriate interpretation is needed. Authenticity includes: (1) Design; (2) Building materials; (3) Tradition builds; (4) Contextual and environmental; (5) Use. The cultural meaning of a building needs to be recaptured through preservation, and security must be guaranteed against damage to buildings that can endanger building users, as well as guarantee of future maintenance. The replacement of lost parts of the building must be harmonious with the original part, but easily recognizable, so as not to falsify historical evidence. Appropriate use is very necessary, so as not to change the layout, building systems, decorating buildings, and not reduce the cultural meaning.

The order of historical buildings and their context is inseparable historical evidence. It is not permissible to move all or part of a building, unless needed for its protection or justified for national or international interests. Conservation should not isolate the building from its context, which might have changed. Conservation should be carried out following the techniques and traditions of building the original, because its sustainability will maintain the continuity of the tradition of the process of building local communities.

D. Preservation Approach Framework

As a summary of the conversation aspects described above, the framework of the conversation approach can be discussed in figure 1.

Figure 1. Framework for a conversation approach [10]

E. Conceptual Framework for Architectural Preservation

The conceptual framework for architectural preservation is the elaboration of the preservation reading framework and architectural framework in figure 2.

Figure 2. Framework for conversation and architecture approaches [10]

The initial stage of elaboration of the preservation framework and architectural framework (figure 3).

Figure 3. The initial stage of elaboration of the architectural-conversation approach framework [10]

The final stage of the elaboration of the preservation framework and the architecture framework becomes the architectural preservation framework, which is called the conceptual framework (figure 4).

Figure 4. Conceptual framework of architectural preservation [10]

III. METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is taking photos of buildings in detail and measurements. The method of taking photos and measuring building elements in detail is useful to know the meaning of their shapes, proportions and architectural styles. Data from the results of photo taking and measurement were then categorized and triangulated. The results of the triangulation of photos and measurements are then compared critically with theories relating to the theme under study, all sources of theory taken as references in this paper have been included in the bibliography. The results of triangulation and comparison can be found in the main elements of the building for preservation.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Pancasila Building is a European building that is quite magnificent on Jalan Hasanudi. The building that is now used by the Pancasila Foundation was once owned by Han Tik Gwan Khong Shu, a Han family gathering. In the building area of more than 1 hectare, there are bongs (tombs) of Han Hoo Tong, the head of the first THHK (Tiong Hwa Hwee Koan) Pasuruan. The Pancasila Foundation is a foundation founded by Chinese Pasuruan residents, some parts of the building are used for schools, have a very stylish Indische Empire building style in the Dutch East Indies in the 19th century. According to Handinoto in "Pasuruan and Chinese Ethnic Architecture of the End of the 19th Century and the Beginning of the 20th Century", this architectural style was very popular at the time, so that almost all types of buildings use it. One of the hallmarks of this architectural style is its excellent adaptation to the humid tropical climate. Almost all ancient Chinese houses in Pasuruan refer to the Indische Empire architectural style, especially the Pancasila Building.

A. Indische Empire Culture

Indische Empire architecture is a style that developed in the 19th century in the Dutch East Indies. The style of architecture was popularized by Governor General HW Deandles (1808-1811). The architectural style known as The Empire Style is a neo-classical architectural style that has hit Europe, especially France. The result is in the style of the colonial East Indies (Indonesia), which is adapted to the local environment with the climate and material availability at that time. Characteristics include: a symmetrical plan, one floor and covered with a shield roof. Other characteristics of this style include: open, there are pillars in the front and back porch, there is a central foyer that leads to another room. A distinctive feature of this architectural style is the existence of rows of pillars or columns (Greek-style) that soar upwards and there are gables and crowns above the front and rear porches. The back porch is often used as a dining room and on the back is connected to the service area.

Figure 5. Front view of the Pancasila Building

B. Column Preservation

The column used in this building is a type of tuscan column which is a simplification of the Doric column. Simple column form without ornaments but has the impression of being sturdy, strong, and mighty. This column is located on the front porch of the building to support the flat roof of the building. At present the total number of Tuscan columns is 4 pairs of columns. Placement of this column has the same distance. The Tuscan column in the Pancasila building consists of large columns made of cast concrete. The existence of this column is a characteristic of the Indische Empire style.

Figure 6. Column sketch

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C. Ornament Preservation

1) Roof ornaments

Figure 7. Sketch of "Crown" ornaments

There is an ornament shaped like a crown at the top of the building that characterizes the Indische Empire style.

Figure 8. Sketch of “Dentil’s” ornaments

The Indische Empire style on the roof is “Dentil” which is a box-shaped repetitive ornament in the bed-mold (center) part of the cornice. Dentil ornaments depict the end of the building rafters.

Figure 9. Sketch “Greek Key” ornaments

At the bottom of the dentil there is an ornament of “Greek Key” or “Greek Fret” which is an important symbol in Greek culture because it is a symbol of immortality.

Figure 10. Sketch of “Banyu Tetes” ornaments

Due to the influence of Javanese culture, Indische Empire's architectural form on the front porch of the building uses “Lisplank” in the form of ornament “Banyu Tetes”.

2) *Canopy support ornaments*

Figure 11. Sketch of canopy support ornaments

If most of the supporting details are in the form of tendrils, this building uses a simpler ornament in the form of circles.

3) *Bouvenlist ornaments*

Figure 12. Ornament sketch for bouvenlist number 1

Figure 13. Ornament sketch for bouvenlist number 2

The entire bouvenlist ornament uses tendrils which are an adaptation of Javanese culture to the Indische Empire style.

4) *Side home ornaments*

Figure 14. Sketch of side porch ornaments

The decoration on this side porch consists of a wooden board arrangement that forms a symmetrical pattern. The wood arrangements produce a curved shape at the bottom.

5) *Plafond ornaments*

Figure 15. Sketch of plafon ornaments

Ornamental on the ceiling reflects a blend of Indische Empire styles and Javanese culture.

6) *Cornice ornaments*

Figure 16. Sketch of cornice ornaments

The combination of columns and arches is a characteristic of Greek architecture.

D. Floor Preservation

Marble and terrazzo floors are one of the flooring materials that were popular during the Indische Empire Style. The characteristics of The Indische Empire Style are seen in the use of terasso and the use of geometric patterns with a grid arrangement and symmetrical

(balanced) and the colors used are dark brown monochromatic, light brown and cream color with black variations.

Figure 17. Picture of marble and terazzo floors

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussions that have been carried out, it can be concluded a number of points regarding the character of the Pasuruan City Pancasila building and its preservation direction. The character of the Pancasila Building in Pasuruan City consists of visual characters that have a predominance of curved shapes on facades and rectangular geometric shapes in the inner space. The discharge of the type, shape and size of openings is along the building envelope on the facade. Visual continuity is achieved by applying decorative arches to building elements.

Preservation direction of the Pancasila Building in Pasuruan City on the assessment of cultural meaning. Buildings that are based on the criteria of aesthetics, care, authenticity, extravagance, historical role and strengthen the image of the region. The results of the assessment of 3 (three) elements with preservation directions are found in fuss, building mass and supporting wall construction, 6 (six) elements with conservation directions are in the door, roof, window, column, building orientation and roof construction, 2 (two) elements with the direction of restoration found on windows and floors, 4 (four) elements of rehabilitation can be found on walls, ceiling doors and space organizations.

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